

REFOREST

Organisation: University of Sopron

HUNGARIAN INTER-LLs WORKSHOP for STAKEHOLDERS-RESEARCHERS

INFORMATION EXCHANGE AND TRAINING

Date 6.7.2023

Vértesacsá, Olaszfalu, Bajti

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An inter-LivingLabs field workshop targeting stakeholders-researchers information exchange and training was organized on 6 July 2023 in Hungary, within the frame of REFOREST project. The Hungarian research group of REFOREST and stakeholders interested in agroforestry visited the three Living Labs which are involved in the project.

For the interested parties, the workshop provided an introduction about the selected living labs: how they work, what ecosystem services they have, what basic factors make successful agroforestry management possible and how the successful family-farm business model based on these systems works. Furthermore, the Hungarian research group of REFOREST examined how the developed research protocol can be optimally integrated into their operation, as well as what other possibilities are available for contributing to the output indicators of the project.

The first station of the field day was the “Valaha Tanya” Farm in Vértesacsá. The owner of the farm introduced his agroforestry system to the group. Four different kind of agroforestry systems can be found on the farm next to each other: silvoarable, wood pasture, shelterbelt and multipurpose trees system (Figure 1-4).

Fig. 1: On-site examining the LL to prepare for field tests (Photo by A. Vágvölgyi)

Fig 2.: Intercropped orchard in Vértesacsza (Photo by A. Vágvölgyi)

Fig. 3: Grazed orchard in Valaha-Tanya farm (Photo by A. Vityi)

Fig. 4: Black locust windbreak around the farm (Photo by A. Vágvölgyi)

In the next location, at Olaszfalu a wood pasture land and the adjacent community forest was visited. The wood pasture covers an area of 20 ha, where horses, sheep, goats and donkeys are grazed, but the farmer has also poultry and pigs (Figure: 5-7). We got acquainted with the history, as well as the geological and cultural values of the wood pasture and the broader, protected environment. While the farmer hosted the group, he explained how he developed his farm services, as a result of which the estate now fulfills the role of heritage conservation, education and training, and professional event venue.

Fig. 5: Field visit in the wood pasture and adjacent community forest at Olaszfalu (Photo by A. Vityi)

Fig. 6: On-site examining the LL to prepare for field tests at Olaszfalu (Photo by A. Vágvölgyi)

Fig. 7: Sheeps grazing in the wood pasture at Olaszfalu (Photo by A. Vágvölgyi)

The third location of the workshop was the Bajti Breeding Yard of the University of Sopron, Forest Research Institute. The agroforestry experimental site was created with plant associations considered unique in Hungary. The system was designed in such a way that, in addition to the application of different ground cover solutions and plants with market value (*Plantago lanceolata*, *Vinca minor*, *Rumex rugosus*) implemented among the poplar tree rows, the various ecosystem services, practical functionality and economic parameters of the system could be examined.

Fig. 8: On-site examining the LL to prepare for field tests in Bajti (Photo by A. Vágvölgyi)

Fig. 9: Alley cropping system based on multiple soil cover and plant association concept – the experimental site of University of Sopron (Photo by A. Vityi)

The group had a brainstorming session including discussion on the data availability and collection methods regarding microclimate and biodiversity of the system and the possibility of conducting further research activities. The first aerial photos taken with a drone have also been created in all Living Labs. The remote images of the agroforestry LL sites will serve as basis for precision monitoring of tree and ecosystem growth which data will be used for feeding the neural networks to be trained and validated within REFOREST. This document represents an updated version of the Dissemination and Exploitation Plan of the ReForest project, outlining a strategic approach, activities, and tools aimed at effectively disseminating project outcomes to a diverse audience of external stakeholders throughout its duration. Scheduled for revision at M36 of the project implementation, this update pursues two primary objectives:

1. Evaluation of the initial version of the plan (D1.3), submitted at M6, to assess its effectiveness.
2. Provision of guidelines for advancing the development and application of communication, dissemination, and exploitation tools and channels available to the consortium to ensure maximum impact of the project activities.

The successful implementation of the ReForest project significantly depends on well-coordinated communication, dissemination, and exploitation efforts implemented jointly by all project partners. An effective Dissemination and Exploitation plan should be dynamic and regularly adjusted in alignment with the project's progression and the increasing engagement of the target groups of the project. The communication and dissemination activities must ensure that all relevant information is both accessible and comprehensible to the appropriate stakeholders.

From the very beginning of the project, the ReForest team has actively participated in diverse onsite and online communication and dissemination activities, including conferences, meetings with local stakeholders, and scientific events. Engaging with farmers, agricultural advisors, policymakers, and the broader public, the ReForest partners aim to bridge the gap between scientific knowledge and the wider public, at the same time strictly adhering to scientific communication principles. Facilitating the understanding of the practical advantages of agroforestry through scientific data, knowledge generated in the project Living Labs across Europe, and active stakeholder engagement via the dedicated ReForest platform support the adoption of agroforestry as land management practice across Europe.